

AS Statistics - Does Posture Affect Audiovisual Learning Comprehension in a Classroom Setting?

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Abstract

Many high-school students choose to adapt various postures during their classes. Understanding how different factors, such as posture or classroom environments, affect learning can help refine teaching strategies and improve educational outcomes. By investigating how posture influences comprehension, educators can better design classroom settings and activities that foster learning. While previous studies have explored aspects of learning environments, few have looked into how specific actions (such as posture) impact cognitive processes during learning. The main objective of this study to examine the effect of body posture on audiovisual learning comprehension in a classroom setting. Specifically, it investigates whether sitting upright improves comprehension and information retention compared to a slouched posture of students at Sonoma Academy. A matched pairs design was used, where 31 high school students watched two educational videos on separate days, each time in a different posture (upright vs. slouched). Comprehension was assessed through standardized tests, and a paired T-test was conducted to analyze the significance of differences in scores. The results showed no significant difference in comprehension scores between the two posture conditions. Although the mean score for the upright posture was slightly higher than for the slouched posture, the confidence interval included zero, indicating that any observed differences were likely due to random variation. These findings suggest that posture alone may not play a significant role in short-term audiovisual learning comprehension. Future research should explore long-term effects and different educational subjects.

Keywords: Posture, Body Language, Learning Comprehension, Audiovisual Learning, Education Research, Cognitive Science, Human Factors in Learning

1 Introduction

How does our body language affect the ways we learn? Students at Sonoma Academy choose to adapt various postures while in a variety of classes, ranging from completely upright to slumped over slouching. The main question that this experiment is trying to answer is whether sitting upright in a classroom setting enhances audiovisual learning comprehension compared to audiovisual learning comprehension when maintaining a slouched posture.

Answering this question gives insight into the mechanisms in which body language affects learning comprehension and information retention. I suggest that compared to a slouched posture, sitting in an upright posture will improve the results of the learning comprehension test and the retention of information. Posture plays an important role in overall body language, and how body language is observed is also important in how an individual comprehends incoming information and is linked to improvements in an academic environment. According to a study published in the American Psychological Association, Reed^[1] states that the learning comprehension test scores are affected on average by the body language assumed by the participant and increase more in seated posture. This study aims to focus on specific improvements an individual can make in relation to their seated posture, as there may be psychological effects associated with slouching or sitting with an upright posture that may transfer over learning comprehension and improvements in classes^[2] that this study hopes to observe. The population sampled for this experiment consists of all students of Sonoma Academy in their respective advisory groups.

2 Design

Advisories sized (n=12) will first be randomly selected to participate in the study. Once selected, the faculty and staff advisory groups will be contacted to provide consent for their advisory to take part in the experiment. After obtaining consent, students within these advisories will be included as participants, ensuring that the sample is randomized and representative of the school community, while minimizing selection bias. Ethics are not an issue for this experiment because the participants are random and there is no potential chance of harm for the said participants. Additionally, the advisors will be informed about the study's purpose and procedure, ensuring transparency and informed consent. Measures will be taken to protect the privacy and confidentiality of the participants' data. This is an experiment because it actively involves manipulating an independent variable—the participant's posture—and measuring its effect on the dependent variable, in this case, the results of a comprehension test. The controlled conditions and the random assignment of postures will ensure that this study tests for causation rather than observing possible correlations. The purpose of this experiment is to examine the effect of body posture in a seated position on audiovisual learn-

ing comprehension in a classroom setting. I hypothesize that sitting upright will improve learning comprehension and information retention when compared to a slouched posture. The independent variables in this experiment are body posture at encoding (sitting upright vs. slouched), while the dependent variable is learning comprehension, measured by standardized test results on audiovisual material.

Data will be collected using a matched pairs design. Initially, advisories will be randomly selected to participate through a simple random sampling method. Each advisory will be assigned a random number, and three advisories will be chosen at random using a random number generator. After selection, the advisors of these groups will be contacted to obtain consent for their advisory to participate in the experiment. This process ensures both randomization in the selection and respect for the advisors' approval. Within each selected advisory, all students will be included, provided they are able to complete both portions of the comprehension tests. Students with scheduling conflicts will be assigned alternative testing days from another advisory, ensuring that they complete the video and comprehension test under the same conditions as the other participants.

The participants consisted of a diverse group of students, including 9 freshmen, 8 sophomores, 4 juniors, and 9 seniors. This range of grade levels provides a varied representation of the student body, allowing for a broader perspective on the study's findings across different levels of academic experience. The general age range for all high school students is between 14-18 years of age^[3], so this study can only infer about students at Sonoma Academy, ages 14-18 years old. Any student unable to attend both testing sessions or make up a missed test will be excluded from the study, as their incomplete data would prevent meaningful comparison in the matched pairs design.

On Day 1 of the experiment, students were randomly assigned to two groups by having them choose a packet from a stack of identical packets. Half of the students selected a packet labeled "slouch" on the inside with an example image (See Figure 1a), while the other half selected a number labeled "straight" (indicating sitting upright) on the inside and an example image (See Figure 1b). There were 36 packets with one assigned to each student, 18 labeled "Slouch" and the other 18 labeled "Straight."

(a) Slouched

(b) Straight

Figure 1: Image of Slouched Posture and Image of Straight Posture Shown on Packets

On Day 1, students watched a short educational video on an obscure topic and completed a comprehension test (See Figure 2a) On Day 2, the students switched postures, with the group that slouched on the first day sitting upright, and the group that sat up straight on the first day slouching. They watched a completely different video and completed a different test with different questions (related to the context of the second video). This randomization through the random packet drawing method ensures balanced representation and minimizes bias in assigning postures. Additionally, the setup of both days were the exact same, with students sitting in their same spots. Sophomores who could not attend the regularly scheduled testing days were given the opportunity to complete the experiment on alternative testing days following the same testing times, conditions, videos, by coordinating with their advisors. This ensures that all participants experience identical

conditions during the study despite the scheduling conflicts. (See Fig 2b)

(a) Regular Testing Day Setup

(b) Alternative Testing Day Setup

Figure 2: Comparison of Regular and Alternative Testing Day Setups

To ensure that the comprehension tests were not testing on preexisting knowledge, the videos chosen were randomly selected on “obscure” topics. Additionally, both videos were around the same duration, with Video 1 being 6 minutes and 40 seconds long while Video 2 was 6 minutes and 46 seconds long. For both videos, participants also had 5 minutes to complete the comprehension tests, which were 15 questions each, ensuring that there was consistency among both videos and tests. Matching students against themselves by having them complete the study on two different days—one with a slouched posture and the other with an upright posture—helps control for individual differences in preexisting comprehension skills. This within-subjects design ensures that each participant serves as their own control, meaning that any differences in comprehension between the two conditions (slouched vs. upright) are more likely to be attributed to the effect of posture rather than differences in baseline abilities.

The study was approved by the Sonoma Academy AS Stats Ethics Committee (Amber Greer), and follows the principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki^[4]. Likewise, informed consent was obtained from all participants, and their data remained strictly confidential. For the release of the study, participants’ information will be anonymized.

Post comprehension test, all the tests were graded by hand and input into an online database, that checked all the grades to make sure that the test scores were accurate.

To assess the impact of body posture on learning comprehension, a paired

T-test was conducted to determine if the mean difference between participants' comprehension scores when sitting upright versus slouching was statistically significant, with $\alpha = 0.05$. This allowed for testing the null hypothesis that there is no difference in learning comprehension between the two postures. The comprehension test scores from both sessions will be compared for each student to determine if there is a significant difference in their performance between the slouching and upright postures. Since each student takes both tests (one while slouching and one while sitting upright), The difference in their scores is given by $\text{Difference}_i = \text{Slouch}_i - \text{Upright}_i$. A negative Difference_i would indicate that the student performed better while sitting upright, supporting the hypothesis. Additionally, a TInterval was used to calculate the 90% confidence interval for the mean difference in scores between the two conditions (slouched vs. upright posture). A 90% confidence level was chosen to estimate the range within which the true mean difference in comprehension scores is likely to fall, providing insight into the precision of the difference observed.

The results will be analyzed in the next section.

3 Results

The experiment examined the effect of body posture (slouched vs. upright) on audiovisual learning comprehension. The results indicate that there is no significant difference in the impacts of a Slouched vs. Upright post on learning comprehension in Sonoma Academy students from the 9th, 10th, 11th, and 12th grades.

3.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 presents the mean comprehension scores and standard deviations for each posture condition.

Condition	Mean (M)	SD	Sample Size (n)
Slouched	63.5%	11.2%	31
Upright	66.3%	10.03%	31

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics for Comprehension Scores

3.2 Checking Conditions for Statistical Tests

Before conducting hypothesis testing, we verify that the necessary conditions for a T-test are met:

- **Random Sample:** The participants were randomly selected from Sonoma Academy advisories, ensuring that the sample is representative of the student body. Initially, $n = 36$ students were selected, but 5 students did not participate, resulting in a final sample size of $n = 31$. Sonoma Academy has a student population of 330 students ^[5]
- **Central Limit Theorem (CLT):** Since $n = 31$ is greater than 30, the CLT applies, meaning that the sampling distribution of the mean difference in comprehension scores can be assumed to be approximately normal.
- **Normal Population Assumption:** The sample was drawn from the student population at Sonoma Academy. Additionally, the boxplot of the distribution in mean comprehension test scores was fairly symmetric, while the normal probability distribution graph was linear. Therefore, we can assume that the sample was drawn from a fairly normal population (See Image 3).
- **10% Condition:** The sample size ($n = 31$) is less than 10% of the total student population at Sonoma Academy (335 students), ensuring that the independence assumption holds.

(a) Normal Probability Plot of the Distribution of Differences in Test Scores (Slouch-Straight).

(b) Boxplot of Score Differences (Slouch-Straight).

Figure 3: Assessing Normality of Sample Data

3.3 Hypothesis Testing

To evaluate the effect of body posture on learning comprehension, the following hypotheses were tested:

- **Null Hypothesis (H_0):** There is no difference in mean comprehension scores between the two posture conditions ($\mu_{\text{Upright}} - \mu_{\text{Slouched}} = 0$).
- **Alternative Hypothesis (H_A):** The mean comprehension score for the upright posture condition is greater than the mean comprehension score for the slouched posture condition ($\mu_{\text{Upright}} - \mu_{\text{Slouched}} > 0$).

3.4 Statistical Analysis

A paired-samples T-test was conducted to compare comprehension scores between posture conditions. The results indicate no significant difference:

$$t(30) = -0.927, \quad p = 0.1807$$

A 90% confidence interval for the mean difference in scores (Upright – Slouched) was calculated via a T-Interval to be:

$$-0.0794 \leq \mu_d \leq 0.0233$$

Discussion: Since the p-value, 0.1807, is greater than $\alpha = 0.05$, we fail to reject the null hypothesis and cannot state that there is a significant difference in audiovisual learning comprehension when sitting up straight versus when in a slouched position. Additionally, since the value for the null hypothesis, $\mu_0 = 0$, falls within our 90% confidence interval of $0.0794 \leq \mu_d \leq 0.0233$, this shows that there is a chance that the true mean difference in comprehension test scores could be zero. Therefore, we cannot conclude that there is a significant difference in audiovisual learning comprehension test scores when sitting up straight versus when in a slouched position.

3.5 Graphical Representation

Figure 4a and Figure 4b illustrate the distribution of comprehension scores for both conditions, demonstrating that the median score in the upright posture condition is higher than in the slouched posture condition.

(a) Distribution of Straight Condition Comprehension Test Scores

(b) Distribution of Slouched Condition Comprehension Test Scores

Figure 4: Comparison of Comprehension Test Score Distributions for Both Conditions

3.6 Difference in Test Scores: Slouch vs. Straight Posture

The mean difference in test scores between the slouched and upright posture conditions was calculated as $D\% = \text{Slouch}\% - \text{Straight}\%$. The mean difference in scores was -0.028, with a standard deviation of 0.1685, based on a sample size of $n = 31$ (See Table 2).

To determine whether this difference is statistically significant, a 90% confidence interval was calculated. The results from the confidence interval suggest that the observed difference in test scores is not significant, and the effect is unlikely to be due to random variation. This conclusion is supported by the statistical analysis, which confirms that there is no significant increase in audiovisual learning comprehension when comparing slouching to sitting up straight.

Measure	Value
Mean Difference	-0.028
Standard Deviation	0.1685
Sample Size (n)	31

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics for the Difference in Test Scores

Figure 5: Distribution of Test Score Differences (Slouch - Straight)

3.7 Summary

Although the mean score on the upright posture comprehension test was higher on average than the slouched posture, there is no significant difference in audiovisual learning comprehension between slouching and sitting upright. The statistical analyses confirm that this difference is not significant, and the confidence interval supports that the observed effect is likely due to random variation.

4 Discussion

4.1 Limitations and Confounding Variables

While this study aimed to examine the effect of body posture on audiovisual learning comprehension, several limitations should be considered. One key weakness is the relatively small sample size ($n = 31$), which may limit the ability to generalize the results. The study did not control for factors like prior GPA, learning disabilities, or past experience with audiovisual material, all of which could have influenced comprehension scores. Additionally, participant motivation and attention levels could have varied across testing days, potentially influencing test performance. Since the study relied on matched pairs design, external factors such as fatigue, prior knowledge, or even different levels of engagement with the audiovisual material could have confounded the results. If students believed that posture influences comprehension, they might have unconsciously performed better or worse based on what they expected, rather than an actual physiological effect of posture.

Another potential confounding variable is the testing environment. Although efforts were made to ensure consistency in video presentation, subtle differences in external distractions (e.g., classroom noise, lighting, or seating position) may have affected comprehension. Additionally, the presence of different instructors or external variables in the alternative testing sessions could have introduced unintended variations in administration style, potentially affecting test-taking behavior. Furthermore, while participants were instructed to maintain a specific posture, we cannot guarantee that they adhered strictly to the assigned slouched or upright positions throughout the video. Although both videos were designed to be of equal difficulty, subtle differences in how engaging or complex the material was could have impacted comprehension scores, and so even though efforts were made to standardize

test difficulty, one test may have been inherently harder or easier than the other.

4.2 Extrapolation of Results

The results of this study suggest that posture may not have a significant impact on audiovisual learning comprehension in a classroom setting. However, the extent to which these findings can be generalized beyond the study population is limited. Since the participants were drawn from Sonoma Academy, factors such as age, cognitive ability, and prior educational background may have influenced the outcomes. Moreover, the content of the comprehension tests was limited to two videos on obscure topics; different subject matter could yield different results. Therefore, while these findings provide insight into short-term learning comprehension of students at Sonoma Academy, they should not be extrapolated to long-term memory retention, real-world academic performance, different age groups, or other schools without further investigation.

4.3 Suggestions for Future Research

To build on the findings of this study, future research could explore several areas:

- **Larger and More Diverse Sample:** Conducting the study with a larger participant pool across multiple schools or educational settings could enhance the possible extrapolation of results and may provide different results.
- **Long-Term Study:** Investigating whether posture affects long-term retention, rather than just short-term comprehension, would provide valuable insights into its potential educational impact.
- **Physiological Measurements :** Incorporating tools such as eye-tracking, heart rate monitoring, or sleep tracking mechanisms could provide objective measures of participant engagement and posture adherence.
- **Different Learning Subjects :** Future studies could explore whether posture influences comprehension in different subject matters or skills, such as reading-based learning, problem-solving tasks, or hands-on activities.

Overall, while this study did not find a significant effect of posture on audiovisual learning comprehension, future research with enhanced methods and larger sample sizes could provide deeper insights into the relationship between body posture and learning outcomes.

5 Conclusion

The results of this study suggest that body posture does not have a significant impact on audiovisual learning comprehension. Although the mean comprehension score was slightly higher when participants sat upright compared to slouching, statistical analysis confirmed that this difference was not significant.

Several confounding factors, such as environmental variables, individual learning differences, and potential distractions, may have influenced the results. Additionally, the relatively small sample size limits these findings.

Future research should consider increasing sample size, standardizing testing environments, and incorporating objective physiological measures to assess engagement. While posture may still play a role in learning under different conditions, this study suggests that its effects on short-term audiovisual comprehension are minimal.

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